

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Web Data Portal v.1.0

Deliverable D7.9

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<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

About this document**Deliverable:** D7.9 Web Data Portal v.1.0**Work Package:** WP7 Data management**Delivery date:** 30 October 2024**Delivery date version 2:** 12 March 2026**Type of document:** Report**Dissemination level:** Public**Lead beneficiary and author:**

PP6 -ETT S.p.A. (ETT): Antonio Novellino, Mariaclaudia Paolini

Contributors (Researchers involved in the deliverable):

All work package leaders and co-leaders.

Review:PP1: Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), Chiara Bearzotti (chb@dmi.dk)**Cover sheet:** SOOSmap ©SOOS**Disclaimer:** Funded by the European Union and UK Research and Innovation. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor UK Research and Innovation can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

History of Changes.....	4
1.Publishable summary	5
2.Work performed and main achievements	5
2.1 Description of the work performed	6
2.1.1 SOOSmap.....	10
2.1.2 Notebooks	13
2.2 References.....	26
2.3 Open Science	26
3. Results	27
4. Impact.....	27

History of Changes

Version	Date	Comment	Authors
Version 1	30 October 2024	Submitted version	Antonio Novellino
Version 2	12 March 2026	Clarifications on the link between the OCEAN ICE and the SOOSmap, and on the integration of OCEAN ICE data in SOOSmap have been added to the section 2.1.1 and 2.1.2. Section 2.1.3, now obsolete, has been removed.	Rachele Bordoni

1. Publishable summary

The goal of OCEAN ICE is to evaluate the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet (AIS) and Southern Ocean processes on sea level rise, deep water formation, and ocean circulation to enhance predictions of how changes in the Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets impact global climate. To achieve this, historical datasets, observations from the period spanning 2022 to 2024, and numerical models, including the development of coupled ice sheet-ocean and ice sheet-ocean-climate models, will be employed.

The WP7 Data Management team is taking over the legacy of the EU Horizon 2020 SO-CHIC project and will contribute to making Southern Ocean data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable in the long term. As described in the OCEAN ICE Data Management Plan (Novellino & Misurale, Deliverable D7.1 - Data Management Plan (v.1), 2023) (Novellino & Dapuzeto, Deliverable D7.2 - Data Management Plan (v.2), 2024), WP7 focuses on in situ data.

The OCEAN ICE data access and visualization services are part of the Application Layer (AL) for data presentation and dissemination described in the OCEAN ICE-DI illustrated in the Deliverable D7.4 Infrastructure Design v.1.0, taking its foundation on data ingestion/connection and data service layer. OCEAN ICE-DI-AL is designed to provide the Southern Ocean community with FAIR information on physical, biochemical and metocean parameters.

2. Work performed and main achievements

OCEAN ICE is focused on assessing the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes on Earth's systems. This assessment seeks to advance the current understanding of the physical, chemical, biological, and meteorological processes occurring within the Arctic and Antarctic oceans and cryosphere. The overall goal of the OCEAN ICE WP7 is to design, develop and operate data management solutions that adhere to FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016; Tanhua et al., 2019), ensure the adoption of best practices, promote interoperability, and facilitate data sharing with a special focus on Southern Ocean.

The critical role of the Southern Ocean in the Earth System highlights the need for sustained, integrated and multidisciplinary observations. Due to the size of the Southern Ocean, this requires international agreement on the priority observations to be collected, and also internationally coordinated data management and delivery. These data and observational needs provided the basis for establishing the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) as a coordinating body to enhance and ensure the delivery of Southern Ocean data across its stakeholders.

OCEAN ICE builds upon and evolves the data management architecture that supports SOOS data sharing, data presentation and data access through the **SOOSmap**¹ data portal. Initiated and developed by the European Marine Observations and Data Network (EMODnet) Physics and the EU H2020 Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate (SO-CHIC)² project (Bricher et al., 2018, Janssen

¹ <https://soosmap.aq/>

² <https://www.sochic-h2020.eu/>

et al., 2023), SOOSmap provides access to observing platforms or sampling events (e.g., an Argo float or plankton trawl).

SOOSmap is a key interface for discovering SOOS data and follows a FAIR data approach. Notably, SOOSmap is designed for in situ data and products, making it the final endpoint for a subset of the OI products. Moreover, OCEAN ICE adheres to open science practices and supports the publication of complementary materials that facilitate the re-use of developed knowledge. One key tool is the OCEAN ICE portal, which not only describes some products but also provides instructions on how to create them using Jupyter Notebook, available for testing and further use under the Google Colab framework.

The following sections describe in summary these features.

2.1 Description of the work performed

During the implementation of the project in 2025 and 2026, the teams have decided not to set up a specific project portal, but rather to integrate the OCEAN ICE datasets within SOOS, in line with the project objective of ensuring interoperability and integration with existing Southern Ocean data infrastructures. Specifically, SOOSmap serves as the entry point for discovering the OCEAN ICE data. This has been later described in the deliverables of WP7 submitted in 2025 and 2026.

In parallel, the WP7 teams have developed a collection of Jupyter Notebooks: <https://s4oceanice.eu/demo/>

SOOSmap and Jupyter Notebooks have clear structures. SOOSmap is developed according to SOOS-SSC and SOOS-DMSC specifications. Jupyter Notebooks, instead, provide reproducible analytical workflows that may rely either on a single dataset or on a curated selection of datasets depending on the objective of the notebook.

Users are mostly interested in searching for information according research topics, location, time periods, and other relevant criteria. SOOSmaps support and facilitate this data discovery by implementing a step-wise selection approach.

Table 1 offers a clear and organized overview of the observational data and modeling efforts that target critical Antarctic and Southern Ocean processes. Observational data collected from in situ platforms and satellite-based instruments, along with data derived from models, are organized according to the scientific challenges outlined by OCEAN ICE and the geographical objects (e.g., Arctic, Antarctic, Ocean, Sea Ice, etc.) describing the system investigated by the project.

Key scientific challenges / Geographic Objects	Category	Observational data collected by in situ platforms and/or satellite-based instruments, or data calculated through models	Antarctic contribution to global mean sea level rise	Antarctic ice sheet dynamics and its climatic triggers about sea level rise	Low-latitude oceans sensitivity to southern sources of deep waters, the AABW	Feedback between northern and southern sources of deep waters and AABW	Potential for future collapse of the ice sheet and as a trigger for further climate tipping points	Antarctica climate variability, surface mass balance	Influence of Antarctic ice sheet dynamics on changes in global & regional temperatures, ocean acidification, sea level rise.	Sea ice and weather forecasting	Link between ice-shelf loss in Antarctica with ocean circulations system e.g. AMOC, and relationship between the relative strength of the ACC and AMOC.
			WP1-3 WP4-6 WP8 WP9	WP1-3 WP2 WP3 WP2-3 WP4 WP5-6	WP1 WP1-2 WP4-5 WP5 WP5-6	WP3-4 WP5 WP6	WP5/6	WP3 WP4	WP2,5,6 WP1-6,8 WP5,6	WP1 WP1,5 WP2 WP3 WP4,6 WP5 WP9	WP1 WP2 WP4 WP6
Sea ice	PHY	Temperature (Cryosphere, Ocean sides), Ice Depth/Thickness (Cryosphere, Ocean sides), Salinity (Cryosphere, Ocean sides), Freeboard, Snow depth, <u>Sea ice production</u>									
Iceberg		Concentration, length									
Ocean Surface	PHY	Sea level, Temperature, Ocean surface height									
	BGC	<u>Length scales and timescales of oxygen isotope ($\delta^{18}O$) variations</u>									
Ice Sheet	PHY	Ice Depth/Thickness									

Key scientific challenges / Geographic Objects	Category	Observational data collected by in situ platforms and/or satellite-based instruments, or data calculated through models	Antarctic contribution to global mean sea level rise	Antarctic ice sheet dynamics and its climatic triggers about sea level rise	Low-latitude oceans sensitivity to southern sources of deep waters, the AABW	Feedback between northern and southern sources of deep waters and AABW	Potential for future collapse of the ice sheet and as a trigger for further climate tipping points	Antarctica climate variability, surface mass balance	Influence of Antarctic ice sheet dynamics on changes in global & regional temperatures, ocean acidification. sea level rise.	Sea ice and weather forecasting	Link between ice-shelf loss in Antarctica with ocean circulations system e.g. AMOC, and relationship between the relative strength of the ACC and AMOC.
			WP1-3 WP4-6 WP8 WP9	WP1-3 WP2 WP3 WP2-3 WP4 WP5-6	WP1 WP1-2 WP4-5 WP5 WP5-6	WP3-4 WP5 WP6	WP5/6	WP3 WP4	WP2,5,6 WP1-6,8 WP5,6	WP1 WP1,5 WP2 WP3 WP4,6 WP5 WP9	WP1 WP2 WP4 WP6
Ice Shelf	PHY	DewFrost Point, Basal melt rate, <u>Basal melting rate</u>									
Snow											
Atmosphere	MET	Humidity, Wind Speed, Gust wind speed, Temperature, Pressure, Short wave downward (GLOBAL) radiation, Precipitation mm/min, Precipitation mm/10 min									

2.1.1 SOOSmap

SOOSmap is integrating different data sources and each source may cover one or more disciplines. Having this huge amount of information fully discoverable under the same data-portal framework requires a certain level of harmonization of the metadata. As part of the OCEAN ICE activities, the minimum set of required metadata was reviewed, updated and applied.

SOOSmap allows users to discover and access circumpolar data coming from several international research centres and data assemblers, oceanographic repositories and marine infrastructures in the Antarctic. Datasets are provided with metadata and are available in multiple data formats drawing from the extensive data holdings of Copernicus and EMODnet, which were collated for European seas but which cover global oceans. Additionally, SOOS is bringing in key datasets of particular value to the Southern Ocean, including krill, plankton, sea ice observations, DNA barcoding, plastics and many more. Currently, SOOSmap incorporates more than 50 data layers including over 50,000 observations.

Briefly, the SOOSmap provides some background layers (bathymetry, regions, altimetry, ice edge, etc) that can be loaded to better locate the area of interest and a matrix filter that enables the user to search by collecting platform (ship, profiler, autonomous vehicle, etc) or by parameter (temperature, salinity, currents, etc). When the user interacts with the filters, a popup presents the available datasets (bottom of the page) which are loaded on the interfaces once selected. Notably SOOS endorsed projects (it is the case of OCEAN ICE) have dedicated cards to be easily identified and awarded.

Fig. 1: SOOSmap landing page.

Fig. 2: SOOSmap interacting with data (platforms).

Fig. 3: SOOSmap interacting with data (parameters).

Fig. 4: SOOSmap interacting with data (endorsed projects – OCEAN ICE data).

Fig. 5: SOOSmap interacting with gridded data/reanalysis.

As part of SOOSmap maintenance, WP7 collects feedback on usability and features that may be improved. For example, there is a clear need to add an additional layer to filter by keywords and key metadata (e.g., project name). In response, the team has introduced a search functionality into the portal, allowing users to easily find datasets by entering partial dataset names (case-sensitive) or by using relevant tags.

2.1.2 Notebooks

Jupyter Notebook is an open-source web application that supports a wide range of programming languages, runs on local machine, and it's possible to access it through any web browser, thus enabling easy and fast knowledge sharing.

The OCEAN ICE WP7 is developing a Jupyter book in Python (<https://github.com/s4oceanice>) offering examples on how to use OCEAN ICE data and products, how to consume these datasets from OCEAN ICE infrastructure, how to implement some reanalysis and how to make chart and graphs. The book is organized in chapter, each chapter is a fully described example and each chapter is linked to a runnable code in Google Colab.

At the time of writing the interfaces is offering the following pages/colabs:

- OCEAN ICE ERDDAP - a tutorial to build queries using Python code and the datasets stored in the OI-DI-SL-ERDDAP.
- Sea Ice Extension³
- Sea Level⁴
- Temperature and Salinity from CTD⁵
- Ocean Circulation, Carbon Uptake, and Environmental Changes⁶
- Informed Climate Insights Through Animal-Borne Sensors⁷

While the following presents one of the exercises, the others can be fully explored through the links in the footnotes.

³ https://s4oceanice.github.io/literacy.s4oceanice/chapters/chapter2/oceanice_ice_sheet.html

⁴ https://s4oceanice.github.io/literacy.s4oceanice/chapters/chapter3/oceanice_sea_level.html

⁵ https://s4oceanice.github.io/literacy.s4oceanice/chapters/chapter4/oceanice_argo_floats.html

⁶ https://s4oceanice.github.io/literacy.s4oceanice/chapters/chapter5/oceanice_cchdo_bottle.html

⁷ https://s4oceanice.github.io/literacy.s4oceanice/chapters/chapter6/oceanice_meop_animal_borne_profiles.html

Analysis of CTD data from Argo profiling floats deployed by the OCEAN:ICE project

For an interactive version of this page please visit the Google Colab:

 [Open in Google Colab](#)

(To open link in new tab press Ctrl + click)

OCEAN:ICE employs a cross-disciplinary, combined observational and modelling approach to achieve its scientific objectives. It melds new in situ measurements, targeted at existing spatial and knowledge gaps, with remote sensed EOs together with a hierarchy of modelling approaches. An ambitious set of quasi-simultaneous circumpolar observations is planned to observe the pathways, properties and high-resolution variability of water masses associated with Antarctic ice-ocean interaction over periods of various years. Several arrays of Argo profiling floats are been deployed as part of this strategy.

The tool uses the following product:

- OCEAN:ICE's ERDDAP (https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE.html)

Mapping OCEAN:ICE deployed Argo Floats

In the next code cell, a map of the Antarctic region will be generated using the Esri Antarctic Basemap projection. The map will display ARGO platforms' sampling locations within the specified time range, marked with unique colors to distinguish each platform. By zooming on the map it is possible to see the trajectory for each Argo platform. The data is fetched from the ERDDAP server, and each platform's sampling points are represented by circle markers. A dropdown menu allows you to select different platforms, updating the current platform value accordingly. Additionally, a legend is displayed to indicate the color associated with each platform.

▼ Hide code cell source

```
# Creating a map with antarctic projection
from ipyleaflet import Map, CircleMarker, basemaps, WMSLayer, projections, MarkerCluster
from ipywidgets import VBox, HBox

m3 = Map(basemap=basemaps.Esri.AntarcticBasemap, crs=projections.EPSG3031.ESRIBasemap, center=[-60, -60])

# Define EPSG:3031 projection
EP = dict(
    name='EPSG:3031',
    custom=True,
    proj4def="proj=stere +lat_0=-90 +lat_ts=-71 +lon_0=0 +k=1
    +x_0=0 +y_0=0 +datum=WGS84 +units=m +no_defs",
    bounds=[[-3174450, -2816050], [2867175, 2406325]]
)

# Define the URL for ERDDAP data
erddap_url = 'https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap'
dataset_id = 'ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE'
data_format = 'csv'
dataset_type = 'tabledap'

# Get minimum and maximum time
csv_info = f'https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/info/ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE/index.csv'
info_df = pd.read_csv(csv_info)
start_time = info_df.loc[info_df['Attribute Name'] == 'time_coverage_start', 'Value'].values[0]
end_time = info_df.loc[info_df['Attribute Name'] == 'time_coverage_end', 'Value'].values[0]

# Construct the full URL for the platforms query
csv_list_of_P = f'{erddap_url}/{dataset_type}/{dataset_id}.{data_format}?PLATFORMCODE&time%2F{start_time}%2F{end_time}'
plist = pd.read_csv(csv_list_of_P, skiprows=[1])
plist_cleaned = plist.dropna()

# Generate distinct colors using the tab20 colormap
cmap = plt.get_cmap('tab20')
num_colors = len(plist_cleaned)
colors = [mcolors.rgb2hex(cmap(i / num_colors)) for i in range(num_colors)]

# Set initial default value for platform
platform = plist_cleaned.iloc[0]['PLATFORMCODE']

# Add ARGO platforms to the map with unique colors
for plat in range(len(plist_cleaned)):
    platform = plist_cleaned.iloc[plat]['PLATFORMCODE']
    csv_url = f'{erddap_url}/{dataset_type}/{dataset_id}.{data_format}?PLATFORMCODE%2F{platform}'

    data = pd.read_csv(csv_url, skiprows=[1])
    data_cleaned = data.dropna()
    sampling_points = data_cleaned.drop_duplicates(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])
```

```

for x in sampling_points.index:
    lat = sampling_points.loc[x, 'latitude']
    lon = sampling_points.loc[x, 'longitude']

    circle_marker = CircleMarker()
    circle_marker.location = (lat, lon)
    circle_marker.radius = 2
    circle_marker.color = colors[plat]
    circle_marker.fill_color = colors[plat]

    m3.add_layer(circle_marker)

# Create HTML legend
legend_html = '<div style="padding: 10px; background: white; border: 1px solid black; font-
legend_html += '<strong>Platform ID Legend</strong><br>'
for plat, color in zip(plist_cleaned['PLATFORMCODE'], colors):
    legend_html += f'<span style="color: {color};">{plat}<br>'
legend_html += '</div>'

# Display map and legend
display(m3)
display(HTML(legend_html))

platform_list = plist_cleaned['PLATFORMCODE'].astype(str).tolist()

platform = platform_list[0]

# Define the dropdown widget
dropdown = widgets.Dropdown(
    options=platform_list,
    value=platform_list[0],
    description='Platform ID:',
    style={'description_width': 'initial'}
)

# Update the platform variable when the dropdown value changes
def on_platform_change(change):
    global platform
    platform = change.new

dropdown.observe(on_platform_change, names='value')

# display(dropdown)

```


ipyleaflet | Imagery provided by NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI); International Bathymetric Chart of the Southern Ocean (IBCSO); General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO).

Platform ID Legend

- 1902687
- 3902582
- 4903780
- 4903786
- 5907087
- 5907093
- 6990621
- 6990622

Analyze the data for the selected Argo Float

In the next code cell, data related to the selected ARGO platform will be fetched from the ERDDAP server. The data includes parameters such as platform code, cycle number, time, latitude, longitude, pressure, temperature, and salinity, along with their respective quality control (QC) flags, which will be filtered to take into account only values with matching QC value of 1. The data is filtered based on the selected time range. After retrieving the data, it is cleaned by removing any missing values and then converted into an xarray dataset for easy manipulation and visualization. The resulting dataset is displayed, showing its contents and structure.

▼ Hide code cell source

```
# Retrieve the data of the selected ARGO FLOAT
file=f"{erddap_url}/{dataset_type}/{dataset_id}.{data_format}?PLATFORMCODE%2Ccycle_number%2C
df = pd.read_csv (file, skiprows=[1])

# Filter selecting only rows with PSAL_QC=1 and TEMP_QC=1
df = df[(df['TEMP_QC'] == 1) & (df['PSAL_QC'] == 1)]

df_cleaned = df.dropna()
prof = xr.Dataset.from_dataframe(df)
# Show the content of the file as an xarray
prof
```

► Dimensions: (index: 792)

▼ Coordinates:

index	(index)	int64	0 1 2 3 4 5 ... 787 788 789 790 791	
--------------	---------	-------	-------------------------------------	---

▼ Data variables:

PLATFORMC...	(index)	int64	1902687 1902687 ... 1902687 1902687	
cycle_number	(index)	int64	1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ... 7 7 7 7 7 7 7 7	
time	(index)	object	'2024-01-12T00:33:00Z' ... '2024...	
latitude	(index)	float64	-74.85 -74.85 ... -74.9 -74.9	
longitude	(index)	float64	-102.4 -102.4 ... -102.3 -102.3	
PRESS	(index)	float64	14.1 23.9 34.0 ... 955.4 964.1	
TEMP	(index)	float64	0.094 0.087 0.028 ... 1.129 1.13	
TEMP_QC	(index)	int64	1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ... 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1	
PSAL	(index)	float64	33.95 33.95 33.96 ... 34.68 34.68	
PSAL_QC	(index)	int64	1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ... 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1	

► Indexes: (1)

► Attributes: (0)

In the next code cell, a scatter plot of sea water temperature versus pressure will be generated for the selected ARGO platform. The x-axis represents the sea water temperature in degrees Celsius (°C), and the y-axis shows the pressure in decibars (dBar). Pressure values are numerically similar (within 2%) to depth in meters below the surface. That is, the pressure at a depth of 1000 meters is about 1000 dbars. The plot allows you to visualize the temperature profile across different depths. The y-axis is inverted to represent deeper depths at the bottom.

▼ Hide code cell source

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(7,5))
scRT = ax.scatter(prof.TEMP, prof.PRESS, s=1, label=f"{platform}")
ax.set_title(f"{platform}")
ax.invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel('Sea Water Temperature (°C)')
plt.ylabel('Pressure (dBar)')
ax.grid()
```


In the next code cell, a scatter plot of salinity versus sea water temperature will be generated for the selected ARGO platform. The x-axis represents salinity in practical salinity units (psu), and the y-axis shows the sea water temperature in degrees Celsius (°C). This plot helps visualize the relationship between salinity and temperature in the ocean.

▼ Hide code cell source

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(7,5))
scRT = ax.scatter(prof.PSAL, prof.TEMP, s=1)
ax.set_title(f"{platform}")
plt.ylabel('Sea Water Temperature (°C)')
plt.xlabel('Practical Salinity (psu)')
ax.grid()
```

Figure

In the next code cell, a Temperature–Salinity (T-S) diagram is created for the selected ARGO platform. The cell calculates the potential temperature at the sea surface level using salinity, in-situ temperature, and pressure data. Salinity values are then plotted against potential temperature, with colors indicating the density of data points.

```

temp = prof.TEMP.values.flatten()
psal = prof.PSAL.values.flatten()
pres = prof.PRESS.values.flatten()

# Compute potential temperature using the seawater package
ptmp = sw.ptmp(psal, temp, pres, pr=0)

# Create bins for the histogram
t_bins = np.linspace(2, 25, 200)
s_bins = np.linspace(35, 37.25, 200)

# Generate a 2D histogram for temperature and salinity
hist, xedges, yedges = np.histogram2d(psal, ptmp, (s_bins, t_bins))
xidx = np.clip(np.digitize(psal, xedges), 0, hist.shape[0] - 1)
yidx = np.clip(np.digitize(ptmp, yedges), 0, hist.shape[1] - 1)
c = hist[xidx, yidx]

# Create the plot
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(7, 5))
sc = ax.scatter(
    psal, ptmp,
    c=c, alpha=0.7,
    cmap='RdBu_r',
    vmin=0.1,
    vmax=10
)
ax.set_title(f"Temperature/Salinity diagram for float {platform}")
ax.set_ylabel("Potential Temperature (°C)")
ax.set_xlabel("Practical Salinity (psu)")
ax.set_ylim(-4, 5)
ax.grid()

# Create a secondary y-axis for potential temperature
ax2 = ax.twinx()
ax2.set_ylim(ax.get_ylim())

# Add a single color bar with a label
cbar = fig.colorbar(sc, ax=ax, label='Density of data points')

# Display the plot
plt.show()

```

Figure

In the next code cell, a vertical salinity section plot is generated for the selected ARGO platform. This scatter plot visualizes the relationship between salinity and temperature, with colors representing the negative pressure values (depth).

The plot helps illustrate how salinity and temperature vary with depth, revealing the water column's stratification and structure. The color gradient indicates how different salinity and temperature combinations are distributed across various depths, providing insights into the oceanographic conditions surrounding the ARGO float. The color bar indicates the depth scale, and grid lines aid in reading the plot.

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```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(7, 5))

# Scatter plot with pressure color-coded
sc = ax.scatter(prof.PSAL, prof.TEMP, c=-prof.PRESS)
ax.set_title(f"Vertical Salinity section for float {platform}")
ax.set_xlabel("Practical Salinity (psu)")
ax.set_ylabel("Sea Water Temperature (°C)")
ax.set_ylim(-4, 5)
ax.grid()

ax2 = ax.twinx()
ax2.set_ylim(ax.get_ylim())

cbar = fig.colorbar(sc, ax=ax, label='Pressure (dBar)')

plt.show()
```

Figure

▼ Hide code cell source

```
vp_fig = None
vp_ax = None

# Function to create the vertical profile plot, to be called on click
def vertical_profile(lat, lon):
    global vp_fig, vp_ax

    if vp_fig is None or vp_ax is None:
        vp_fig, vp_ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(6, 6))
        vp_ax.set_xlabel('Sea Water Temperature (°C)')
        vp_ax.set_ylabel('Pressure (dBar)')
        vp_ax.invert_yaxis()
        vp_ax.grid()

    vp_ax.clear()

    distances = (prof.latitude - lat) ** 2 + (prof.longitude - lon) ** 2
    matching_points = distances <= 1e-4

    if matching_points.sum() > 0:
        temperature = prof.TEMP.values[matching_points]
        pressure = prof.PRESS.values[matching_points]

        # Plot the vertical profile
        vp_ax.scatter(temperature, pressure, s=1, label=f"{platform}")
        vp_ax.set_title(f"{platform} - Latitude: {lat:.2f}, Longitude: {lon:.2f}")
        vp_ax.set_xlabel('Sea Water Temperature (°C)')
        vp_ax.set_ylabel('Pressure (dBar)')
        vp_ax.invert_yaxis()
        vp_ax.grid()
        vp_fig.canvas.draw()
    else:
        print(f"No matching data found for Latitude: {lat}, Longitude: {lon}")

def on_point_click(event):
    if isinstance(event, PickEvent):
        xdata, ydata = event.artist.get_data()
        xclick, yclick = event.mouseevent.xdata, event.mouseevent.ydata

        longitude = xclick
        latitude = yclick

        distances = (xdata - xclick) ** 2 + (ydata - yclick) ** 2
        index = np.argmin(distances)
        longitude = prof.longitude.values[index]
        latitude = prof.latitude.values[index]
        vertical_profile(latitude, longitude)
```

```

# Create and display the trajectory plot
fig_1, ax_1 = plt.subplots(subplot_kw={'projection': ccrs.PlateCarree()})

def set_map_extent(ax, lon_min, lon_max, lat_min, lat_max):
    ax.set_extent([lon_min, lon_max, lat_min, lat_max], crs=ccrs.PlateCarree())

def get_map_extent(prof):
    lon_min = prof.longitude.min().values
    lon_max = prof.longitude.max().values
    lat_min = prof.latitude.min().values
    lat_max = prof.latitude.max().values
    return lon_min, lon_max, lat_min, lat_max

# Set the map extent based on the data
lon_min, lon_max, lat_min, lat_max = get_map_extent(prof)
set_map_extent(ax_1, lon_min-0.5, lon_max+0.5, lat_min-0.5, lat_max+0.5)

# Plot your data points
scatter = ax_1.plot(prof.longitude, prof.latitude, 'ob', picker=True)
ax_1.plot(prof.longitude, prof.latitude, '-b')
ax_1.plot(prof.longitude[0], prof.latitude[0], 'ok')
ax_1.plot(prof.longitude[-1], prof.latitude[-1], 'sk')

# Add map features
ax_1.add_feature(cfeature.LAND)
ax_1.add_feature(cfeature.COASTLINE, edgecolor='white')
ax_1.set_title(f"Trajectory of {platform}", y=-1)
ax_1.gridlines(draw_labels=True, dms=True, x_inline=False, y_inline=False)

# Connect the click event to the figure canvas
fig_1.canvas.mpl_connect('pick_event', on_point_click)

# Display the plot
plt.show()

```

Figure

Data visualization for all the platforms

In the next code cell, a vertical temperature profile plot is created for multiple ARGO platforms. Each ARGO float's temperature versus pressure data is plotted as a scatter plot, with different colors representing different platforms.

The plot shows how the temperature varies with depth (pressure) for each platform, allowing for comparisons across multiple floats. Each platform's data points are color-coded according to a pre-defined color scheme, and a legend is provided to distinguish between the platforms. The y-axis is inverted to correctly represent increasing depth downward.

▼ Hide code cell source

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(8,6))

for plat in range(len(plist_cleaned)):
    plat_code = plist_cleaned.loc[plat, 'PLATFORMCODE']

    file=f"{erddap_url}/{dataset_type}/{dataset_id}.{data_format}?PLATFORMCODE%2Ccycle_numbers"
    df = pd.read_csv (file, skiprows=[1])
    df_cleaned = df.dropna()
    pro = xr.Dataset.from_dataframe(df)
    cols = str(colors[plat])

    verticalT = ax.scatter(pro.TEMP, pro.PRESS, s=1, color = cols, label=f"{plat_code}")

ax.invert_yaxis()
plt.xlabel('Sea Water Temperature (°C)')
plt.ylabel('Pressure (dBar)')
ax.grid()

plt.subplots_adjust(right=0.75)

plt.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left', borderaxespad=0.)

plt.show()
```

Figure

In the next code cell, a scatter plot is generated to visualize the relationship between salinity and potential temperature across multiple ARGO platforms. Each platform's data is plotted with distinct colors to represent different floats.

The plot shows salinity on the x-axis and potential temperature on the y-axis. The salinity and temperature data points are color-coded according to a pre-defined color scheme, which corresponds to different ARGO platforms. The x-axis is limited to a range of 33 to 37 psu, and the y-axis is constrained between -4 and 5 °C to focus on the relevant data ranges.

This visualization helps to compare the salinity and potential temperature characteristics of different ARGO platforms within the specified dataset.

▼ Hide code cell source

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(8,6))

for plat in range(len(plist_cleaned)):
    plat_code = plist_cleaned.loc[plat, 'PLATFORMCODE']

    file=f"{erddap_url}/{dataset_type}/{dataset_id}.{data_format}?PLATFORMCODE%2Ccycle_number"
    df = pd.read_csv (file, skiprows=[1])
    df_cleaned = df.dropna()
    pro = xr.Dataset.from_dataframe(df)
    cols = str(colors[plat])

    verticalT = ax.scatter(pro.PSAL, pro.TEMP, s=1, color = cols, label=f"{plat_code}")

plt.xlabel('Practical Salinity (psu)')
plt.ylabel('Potential Temperature (°C)')
ax.set_ylim (-4, 5)
ax.set_xlim (33, 37)

ax.grid()
plt.subplots_adjust(right=0.75)
plt.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left', borderaxespad=0.)
plt.show()
```

Figure

Additional resources

The Python libraries that have been used in this notebook are:

- [cartopy](#)
- [ipywidgets](#)
- [jupyter](#)
- [requests](#)
- [seawater](#)
- [numpy](#)
- [pandas](#)
- [traitlets](#)
- [matplotlib](#)
- [IPython](#)

Previous

< [Analysis of Antarctic Sea Level: Monthly Mean](#)

Next

[Assessing Ocean Circulation, Carbon Uptake, and Environmental Changes](#) >

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2.2 References

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2.3 Open Science

The implementation of open access in the SOOSmap portal is essential for several reasons:

- **Enhanced Collaboration:** Open access promotes cooperation among researchers, institutions, and the public, facilitating a more collaborative research ecosystem.

- **Increased Visibility:** By making data freely available, we increase the likelihood of citations and utilization, thereby enhancing the impact of research findings.
- **Accelerated Discovery:** Open access allows for quicker dissemination of information, leading to faster advancements in scientific research and innovation.
- **Public Trust:** Transparency in research processes builds public confidence in scientific endeavours, ensuring that findings are accessible for verification and scrutiny.

Our commitment to open access aligns with the principles of open science, which advocate for transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility in research. By providing open access to data and metadata, we contribute to a culture of openness that benefits the entire scientific community. The web portal demo adheres to various open data policies and guidelines, including the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). These principles guide the organization and accessibility of our datasets, ensuring that they can be easily discovered and utilized by all users. To facilitate open access, the web portal design features that are either already visible in the demo or are planned to be developed for the final version:

- **User-Friendly Navigation:** An intuitive interface allows users to easily browse and discover datasets and metadata.
- **Clear Licensing Information:** Each dataset includes in the metadata licensing details that clarify how the data can be used, promoting responsible data sharing.
- **Download Options:** Users can easily download datasets in various formats, ensuring compatibility with different tools and applications.

The portal employs standardized metadata formats to enhance discoverability and interoperability. By following established metadata standards, we ensure that users can easily find, understand, and utilize the available data. Engagement with the user community is a priority.

We encourage feedback from the partners through mechanisms that allow users to suggest improvements or report issues, fostering a sense of ownership and collaboration around the open access initiative.

3. Results

- **SOOSmap:** <https://soosmap.ag>
- **Notebooks:** <https://s4oceanice.eu/demo/> and <https://github.com/s4oceanice/literacy.s4oceanice>

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

OCEAN: CE WP7 is actively achieving Objective 7 (O7) by establishing a robust data infrastructure that ensures free and open access to all data generated. This infrastructure is designed to support FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles and is fully compliant with INSPIRE

regulations. By closely integrating with SOOS, EMODnet, and Copernicus data delivery services, the project facilitates seamless data consolidation and delivery. Additionally, OCEAN ICE is collaborating with key stakeholders -including SOOS (Southern Ocean Observing System), SAMOC (South Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation), EPB (European Polar Board), the EU Polar Cluster, and EU-PolarNet2 -to ensure that data practices align with international standards and contribute meaningfully to global climate assessments and policymaking. Through direct partnerships and the involvement of investigators in international science coordination, climate assessment, and policy bodies, the project is setting and adapting metadata standards and proposing best practices that enhance the reach and impact of its data across these diverse communities.